

On Internet News Translation under Nord's Text Analysis Model ---Taking "Paris Olympics 2024: Locals ask if they're worth the trouble" Reported by BBC as an Example

Zhang Xiaoyu^{1,*}

¹Department of Foreign Languages, Xinjiang University, Urumqi 830000, China

*Corresponding author Email: 1225521524@qq.com

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Abstract: With the progress and development of Internet technology, the cause of Internet news media is growing. With the pace of globalization, China and the world are constantly strengthening their exchanges and contacts. News reports help the general public to understand the current hot news, and the development of the Internet also makes news reports reappear in a new form, that is, network news reports. Based on Nord's text analysis model, this paper discusses the translation methods and strategies of online news texts. This paper aims to provide effective guidance and reference for the translation of online news texts, and hopes that translators can promote international cultural exchanges and contacts in the process of translating such texts.

Key words: Nord, Text analysis mode, Network news, Translation

1. Introduction

Nord is the second generation representative of German Functionalist School. Following the development of Reiss's text type theory, Nord further put forward her own text analysis model. Nord's Text Analysis Model is based on her book *Text Analysis Model in Translation: Theories, Methods and Teaching Applications*, which elaborates the theoretical basis of the Text Analysis Model in Translation, and explains the role and function of source text analysis in translation, then focuses on the basic elements of source text analysis, and finally discusses the application of the analysis model. ^[1]At the same time, Nord mainly analyzes a series of complex and related factors inside and outside the source text in her works. Translators' analysis of the source text plays a guiding role in translation. On the one hand, they can understand the purpose and function of the source text more clearly, so that translators can understand the source text more thoroughly; On the other hand, it can interpret the source text

more accurately, guide translators to adopt translation strategies suitable for the purpose and function of the source text, guide translation practice and improve translation quality.

The textual factors that Nord focuses on are mainly intra-textual factors and extra-textual factors. The factors outside the text include: sender, sender's intention, receiver's expectation, text medium, communication place, communication time, communication motivation and text function; The intra-textual factors include theme, content, presupposition, text composition, non-linguistic factors, vocabulary, sentence structure and suprasegmental features.^[2] Nord once said in her book: "She hopes to have a translation-oriented text analysis model to help translators solve some problems in the process of translation. This pattern has the following two characteristics: Firstly, it is very general and can be applied to all text analysis; Secondly, it is very specific and can analyze various translation problems. Among them, the factors outside and inside complement each other, forming a set of scientific and comprehensive text analysis mode. What kind of text belongs to and how the translator's comprehension ability will not affect the effectiveness of the text analysis model".^[3] However, her proposal of this model just confirms her own hope. This text analysis model is not only a detailed analysis model, but also adds elements of text analysis, so that this model can be used to analyze sentences and text constituent units above sentence level in texts.

2. Case analysis

The case analysis is selected from BBC, a report titled "Paris Olympics 2024: Locals ask if they're worth the trouble". The news mainly discussed from three perspectives, including the mayor of Paris, the chief of police, the citizens living in Paris. They discussed whether the opening of the Olympic Games in Paris has won the support of the majority of Parisians, and also expresses the confidence and determination of the Olympic athletes to the success of the games.

As network news, its main means is to convey information to the public in a timely manner through network media. With the development of the Internet, network media has also spread rapidly around the world, and it acts as a link and a way to enhance the soft power of a country's culture. Therefore, the translation of network news texts requires translators to realize cultural exchange and communication between countries on the basis of paying attention to the principles of news translation.

2.1. Extra-textual factors

The translator selects the sender's intention, the expectation of the recipient and the function of the text, and analyzes them from these three aspects, so as to realize the intention and purpose of the original news report, transmit the news information content to the readers, and help readers understand the in-depth report of relevant current events in the text, the follow-up events, and the attitudes and comments of people on the news and foreign media on the news in the report. In view of how to

translate the extra-textual factors into online news reports, the translator mainly starts from these three aspects in order to meet the needs and expectations of readers and achieve the purpose of online news translation. In this process, the translator should not only transmit the original information, but also pay attention to the readers' requirements and "tastes" in the translated text, so as to decide what translation methods and strategies to choose to meet the needs of the audience. [4] From the example of Wilke and Rosenberger (1994) took a leadership role in delving into the issue of the process that news translation is expected to involve before it is to be officially published in the target culture. After undergoing a study on a wide range of news collections by the Associated Press, they finally concluded that in when foreign news are translated and released in Germany, the texts were adapted to the specific journalistic style of the target language and culture. [5]

2.1. 1. Implementing sender's intention

The use of sender's intention in this network news report is mainly reflected in a large number of direct quotations. In the BBC's quotation of a large number of relevant figures in the original news reports, its role is mainly reflected in two aspects: on the one hand, it can enhance the authenticity and objectivity of the article; On the other hand, we can also express their true attitude and evaluation of this incident through the original words of the characters. Translators adopt literal translation and flexible transformation in the translation of direct speech in order to make the original content information more truly transmitted and introduced to readers.

Sample 1

SL: "How long is it before the police chief simply asks us Parisians to leave the city?" another inhabitant asked on social media.

TL:另一位居民在社交媒体上问道：“警察局长还要多久才要求我们巴黎人离开这座城市？”

Analysis: Direct speech is involved in this sentence. Its content expresses the strong will of the citizens of Paris in France to leave Paris and the view that the citizens are eager for the government to ask them to leave directly. The translator adopts literal translation, which directly and truly reveals the attitudes and viewpoints of the relevant characters in the original text, and retains the attitudes and emotions that citizens want to express.

2.1. 2. Achieving recipient expectations

In this news report, the recipient refers to the target text readers. In the process of reading, the target text readers mainly get the content information and understand the deep meaning expressed in the text. However, the translation methods that the translator can adopt in the translation can be free translation, compilation or parting, etc., in order to realize the deep transmission of the original information, Achieve the expected effect of the recipient.

Sample 2

SL: Are Parisians falling out of love with their own Olympic Games?

TL: 巴黎人是否对自己国家举办的奥运会失去了信心?

Analysis: This example is an interrogative sentence, which expresses the questions of the news media about the public and Parisians. In the process of translation, the translator adopts the translation method of free translation. The translator translate the phrase “falling out of” into “失去”, and the original meaning of this phrase is “giving up”, which is actually a free translation. The translator translates the word “love” into “confidence”, which makes the translation easier for readers to understand and accept after extending and expanding its meaning. At the same time, to a certain extent, it also It is in line with the reading expectations and reading habits of the target readers.

2.1.3. Implementing text functionality

There are three main functions of text: referential function, expressive function and appealing function. Among them, referential function is information function, which conveys the information of the source text, and it refers to the information function of the text, which conveys the information content of the original text. In this network news report, one of its main sub-functions is the informing function, which conveys the facts listed in the text to the target readers truly and accurately. ^[6]Terrance Henry (2009) and Christopher Augustin (2010) believe that the communicative function of text can make a comprehensive analysis of text from the perspective of text structure in a more systematic way^[7], which helps to grasp the core information of the text as a whole. Combining with examples, this paper analyzes why it is more beneficial to realize the communicative purpose of text from the perspective of discourse.^[8]Therefore, network news reports should start from the text and start from the function of the text, so as to study the function and purpose of the translated content.

Sample 3

SL: And an Odoxa opinion poll showed that nearly one in two Frangiliens-inhabitants of the Paris region-now thought the Games were a “bad thing”. The 44% negative rating was double what it was in 2021.

TL: 奥多克萨公司的一项民意调查显示, 近一半的法国人(巴黎地区的居民)现在都认为奥运会是一件“坏事”。对奥运会的负面评价达 44%, 是 2021 年的两倍。

Analysis: “As a text for the purpose of accurately and quickly conveying information, news reports are always based on facts, focusing on spreading news facts and speaking with facts”. ^[9]However, this sentence belongs to the typical text with information function in news reports. In the translation of expressing information function, the translator still adopts literal translation method, which is helpful to the authenticity of the original information transmission, and the translation of data information in the text is a manifestation of the authenticity of information.

2.2. Intra-textual factors

Intra-textual factors the translator mainly analyzes and studies the presupposition, vocabulary and sentences in the news report, and explores the translation strategies and methods adopted in the translation process. Nord thinks that the presupposition of text refers to the communicative level, that is, the presupposition that makes the speech go on, and it is also the presupposition that the speaker assumes existence and thinks the audience can accept it. In this news report, some presupposition are mainly related to political and historical events themselves and common platforms in daily life. At the lexical level, there are some proper nouns, names of people, places, etc., and there are also some four-character words to express emotions. At the sentence level, we can see that there are some long and difficult sentences and passive sentences in the news report, which are long and informative.

2.2. 1. Presupposition

The presupposition is that the information outside the language is not expressed in language, so the presupposition can not be intuitively reflected from the text. ^[10]In news reports, there are some assumptions that the recipients of the source text can understand and accept, but sometimes they may be unknown to the recipients of the target text. Therefore, in the process of translation, the translator needs to understand the presupposition of situational communication, try to make the target text easy for readers to accept and understand, and at the same time, the translator needs to supplement the background information appropriately to explain the content information expressed by the presupposition of the original text.

Sample 4

SL: But summer 2024 promises more of a clear-out than ever, not least because of the tempting deals being offered on Airbnb and other platforms. Rentals during the Games are up to four times normal rates, and it is hard to find a Parisian who is not at least considering the windfall.

TL:但 2024 年夏天的空房率将超过以往任何时候，尤其是因为爱彼迎（Airbnb 指全球民宿短租公寓预订平台）和其他平台上提供的超值优惠活动。奥运会期间的租金是平时正常价格的四倍，很难找到一个不爱这笔意外之财的巴黎人。

Sample 5

SL: There was always a solid corpus of French people who opposed the Games on the lift-wing grounds that they are a colossal waste of money and serve mainly the interests of the multinationals.

TL:一直以来，总有一大批持左翼立场（政治术语，左翼的支持者多认为社会存在不合理的不公平，且这类现象需要被减少或消除。）的法国人反对奥运会，他们的理由是奥运会浪费钱且认为奥运会主要为跨国公司的利益服务。

Analysis:In Examples 4 and 5, the translator is interested in the “Airbnb” and “the lift-wing grounds” is to supplement information, explaining that “Airbnb” refers to the global booking platform for short rent apartments of homestays, while “the lift-wing grounds” is a political term, and most supporters of

the left think that there are unreasonable unfairness in society, and this kind of phenomenon needs to be reduced or eliminated. Based on the translator's understanding of the communicative situation of the original text and the way of supplementing background information, the presupposition in the text can be clearly reproduced, and the communicative effect can be achieved at the same time.

2.2.2. Translated vocabulary

- Four-character grid:

In order to meet the needs of different audiences, international news topics are domesticated in different countries, and they are often distributed and broadcast from national and local perspectives.

^[11]In this news report, there are a large number of words expressing feelings in the original text, which are used by the translator in the translation to convey its emotional attitude, which is more in line with the language features and reading habits of the target readers.

Sample 6

SL: “Paris will be unbearable,” she adds. “Impossible to park; impossible to move around, impossible to do anything. Madame Hidalgo has wrecked Paris, and I want no part of the Games.”

TL:她补充道，“巴黎将令人难以忍受”，“无法停车；无法四处走动，无法做任何事情。伊达尔戈夫人毁了巴黎，我并不想参与其中。”

Sample 7

SL: Take transport. Mayor Hidalgo certainly set Olympic hearts racing with her dire warnings about lack of preparation.

TL:就拿交通工具来说吧。伊达尔戈市长对准备不足发出了可怕的警告，这无疑让奥运选手们心急如焚。

Analysis:In these two examples, after analyzing the original text to understand the emotional attitude expressed by the characters in the text, the translator translated the word “unbearable”, which originally meant “very unbearable to something” into “不堪忍受的”, the phrase “part of the Games” into “参与其中” according to the emotional attitude, and finally the translation of “心急如焚” was paraphrased into the idiom by understanding the situational context of the original text. The translation methods of the four-character case mentioned above are all in line with the language expression habits of the target text, and in news translation, they reflect their translation characteristics.

- Names of persons, places and institutions:

The transliteration of people's names and place names in English should be unified, and they all have their own conventional translation methods. In order to convey the original content information, translators only need to find relevant materials and apply the existing translation. However, when dealing with some specialized words and terms, the general method used is the untranslated method. Some uncertain and unpredictable factors that are most confusing and difficult to deal with in communication will no longer exist, effectively reducing “uncertainty” .^[12]

Sample 8

SL: First the city's own Mayor Anne Hidalgo said out of the blue that transport for next summer's Games would "not be ready in time".

TL:首先，巴黎市长安妮·伊达尔戈（Anne Hidalgo）突然表示，明年夏天奥运会的交通将“无法及时准备好”。

Sample 9

SL: It is hard not to agree with the veteran French athlete and IOC member Guy Drut when he says: "Believe me, the nearer we get to the actual Games, the more of these rows there are going to be."

TL:法国资深运动员、国际奥委会委员盖伊·德鲁特（Guy Drut）说的话很难不令人趋同，他说：“相信我，我们离真正的奥运会越近，这样的争议就会越多。”

Analysis:There are people in both of the above examples. For names, place names and organization names, transliteration is the usual translation method for names, while for organization names, the real meaning can be translated, which also has specific translation expressions for organization names in this example sentence. What translators need to do is to obtain their translations with the help of Internet resources and dictionaries.

2.2.3. Translate sentences

▪ Voice conversion:

Passive voice is often used in English, with objects as subjects. However, for Chinese, the voice is usually active and the subject is human. Therefore, in this process, the translator analyzes some passive sentences by analyzing the usage of voice in the original text. In the translation, the translator adopts a passive and active translation method, which makes the translation more in line with Chinese expression and writing.

Sample 10

SL: Then it was announced that far from buses and metros being free for competition ticket-holders-as promised in the Paris bid for the Games-fares will actually double for the six weeks of the Olympics and Paralympics.

TL: 随后又宣布，公共汽车和地铁不仅不会像巴黎申办奥运会时所承诺的那样对比赛门票的持有者免费，反而会在为期六周的奥运会和残奥会期间翻倍。

Sample 11

SL: So should the organisers be worried? Probably not. Most of the concerns are either exaggerated or easily resolved. And what Games ever took place without mega-jitters in the months ahead?

TL: 那么组织者应该担心吗？也许不必。大多数担忧要么夸夸其词了，要么就很容易解决。有哪一届奥运会在举行之前的几个月里没有出现过巨大的紧张感呢？

Analysis:In examples 10 and 11, it is obvious that there are passive sentences in the original text. However, there are generally four ways to translate passive sentences. The first is to transform them into

judgment sentences in Chinese, the second is to translate them into active sentences, the third is to translate them into ownerless sentences, and finally to translate them into passive sentences in Chinese, such as sentences with structures such as “为……所”. In the above two examples, the translator adopted the second method, translating it into an active sentence, without using the word “被”, which obviously expresses the voice. On the whole, it not only expresses the semantics of the original text, but also makes the sentences more fluent and natural, which conforms to the expression characteristics of online news report translation.

- Split and reorganize:

There are some long sentences in this report, which express a large amount of information and have complex sentence structure. This is also the typical stereotype of news reports—long, subordinate and closely connected.^[9]In this regard, the translator mainly adopts the translation method of disassembling and merging sentences to rearrange the sentence structure, so that the logical relationship between sentences can be clearly expressed, and the translated text can get rid of people's stereotype of news reports.

Sample 12

SL: Of course in any normal year Paris in July and August is already forsaken by a large part of its population, who prefer their second homes in the country or on the coast—that's why the city seems so pleasantly empty to visitors.

TL: 当然，在任何正常的年份里，七八月份的巴黎已经被大部分人抛弃了，他们更喜欢在乡下或海边的第二故乡居住，这也是为什么这座城市对游客来说显得如此空旷的原因。

Sample 13

SL: The transport ticket price controversy is also unlikely to turn Parisians off the Games—not least because the millions of Parisians who have monthly or yearly passes will be unaffected. The cost of all those extra Olympic buses and trains will be borne mainly by visitors—and who cares about them?

TL: 交通票价的争议也不太可能让巴黎人远离奥运会——尤其是因为数百万持有月票或年票的巴黎人不会受到影响。所有这些额外的奥运巴士和火车的费用将主要由游客来承担——谁会在乎他们呢？

Analysis:The analysis of the long and difficult sentences in the above two examples mainly focuses on the ambiguity of the subject referred to by the relative words in the attributive clauses, which requires the translator to read and understand repeatedly, disassemble the sentences and find their subjects. In addition, the translation of dashes in the text is also a point that translators should pay attention to. In the second long and difficult sentence, the translator skillfully uses dashes to explain the information of the original sentence clearly, and the logic of the sentence is more in line with the understanding of the target readers, which makes the translated text reported by the news media more vivid.

3. Conclusion

Under the background of globalization, the network news media reports have achieved effective exchanges and communication between different places, and at the same time, it is also conducive to understanding the cultures of different countries on the cultural level. This paper combines Nord' s text analysis model with network news text, on the one hand, it discusses the text characteristics of network news and the text functions of this type of text; On the other hand, it discusses the translation methods that should be selected for this type of text and the points that translators should focus on in the process of translation, so as to achieve the expected goals and effects for readers of online news translation.

To sum up, this study on the translation of online news texts based on Nord' s text analysis model has a certain guiding role for translators to translate such related texts, and can also help translators have a deeper understanding of the internal and external causes of online news texts and translate more comprehensive and appropriate news content.

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